

Comparison of Gastric Emptying Time Using Ultrasonography with Different Volumes of Clear Fluids

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ABSTRACT

Preoperative fasting helps reduce the risk of aspiration under anaesthesia. This study aimed to compare gastric emptying time after different volumes of clear fluids using ultrasonography. A prospective, randomised, controlled study was conducted on 180 patients aged 18–65 years (ASA I/II) scheduled for elective surgery. Patients were divided into three groups: Group A (3 ml/kg of 5% dextrose), Group B (4 ml/kg of 5% dextrose), and Group C (Control - no fluid). Ultrasonographic assessment of gastric antrum was done in supine and right lateral decubitus positions. Antral cross-sectional area (CSA) and gastric volume were calculated using validated formulas. The ANOVA test was applied and chi square test was used for qualitative data comparison of all clinical indicators with level of significance set at $P < 0.05$. Baseline CSA and gastric volumes were comparable across groups. Gastric volume returned to baseline within 90 minutes in Group A and 105 minutes in Group B. No aspiration events or significant haemodynamic changes were observed. Gastric emptying time after consumption of 3–4 ml/kg of clear fluids is within safe limits for elective surgery. Ultrasonography can guide safe fasting durations and fluid allowance.

Keywords: Gastric Emptying, Ultrasonography, Preoperative Fasting, Clear Fluids, Anaesthesia

INTRODUCTION

Preoperative fasting time is the minimum requirement before sedation or general anaesthesia where patients are not allowed to take solids or liquids orally for the conduct of a safe anaesthesia and surgery. Its importance lies in the fact that this fasting period helps to prevent anaesthesia related pulmonary aspiration which can in turn result in pneumonia and respiratory failure. Risk of aspiration increases with age, physical status, comorbidities like diabetes mellitus, thyroid dysfunction, pregnancy, head injury, opioid therapy etc⁽¹⁾. The delay in gastric emptying is also seen in patients with liver and kidney failure as well as critically ill patients attributed to the delayed gastric emptying.⁽²⁾

The most feared complication of inadequate fasting is aspiration pneumonia which is defined as the acute lung infection occurred as a result of aspiration or regurgitation of gastric content into the lung and it is associated with symptoms like fever, tachycardia and difficulty in breathing⁽³⁾.

Ultrasonography techniques in recent years, have been used for analysis of gastric contents particularly their nature and volumes and this technique enabled real time assessment of gastrointestinal disorders and identify the pathology associated with it⁽⁴⁾ as well as non-invasive measurement of gastric volumes. It also helps in gastric content analysis without significant risk of aspiration and to identify risk population for aspiration during anaesthesia. Compared to other radiological modalities ultrasonography enables portability, cost effectiveness, feasibility repeating the study. Prolonged fasting was associated with various side effects such as fatigueless, dehydration, hypoglycaemia, headache, nausea which added to patient stress and reduced patient compliance. This also affected negatively on pre-operative and intraoperative management. Enhanced recovery after surgery (ERAS) protocol advocated to avoid prolonged fasting and early initiation of oral feed after surgery for improved outcome.⁽⁵⁾

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Accordingly Indian society of anaesthesiologist in 2020 recommended minimum fasting time for optimisation of various gastric contents. 2 hours of fasting prior to surgery was recommended for clear fluids subject to volumes of less than 450 ml of fluid that can be consumed. They also advised for a minimum of 4 hour fasting in case of non - clear fluids.⁽⁶⁾ Pre-operative fasting helps to avoid risk associated with prolonged fasting, reduced patient stress and improved intraoperative and post-operative outcome. Even though maximum recommended volumes allowed for preventing aspiration is specified. Our study aimed to identify the relation between change in volumes of oral fluids consumed to the difference in gastric emptying time to identify if lesser volumes of fluid is associated with lesser pre-operative fasting. In this study we formed two groups of patients and advised to consume two different quantity of fluid according to their weight and assessed the gastric emptying time using ultrasonography and to ascertain the effective change in gastric emptying time with different volumes.

This study aims to compare

1. To compare gastric emptying time for different volumes of clear oral fluid with ultrasonography.
2. To compare the residual volumes in stomach with different volumes of oral fluids after gastric emptying.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

It is a prospective randomized control study conducted in department of anaesthesia, over a period of 18 months from March 2023 to August 2024 after being approved by institutional ethics committee. Written and informed consent were taken from all patients before enrolment and the study was conducted under supervision of experienced anaesthesiologist

A total of 180 patients posted for elective surgeries who satisfied inclusion criteria were selected and divided in three groups.

1. Group 1 - (n=60) will receive 5% dextrose at 3ml/kg.
2. Group 2 - (n=60) will receive 5% dextrose at 4ml/kg.

3. Group 3 - (n=60) control group will receive no fluid

Randomization was done using computer generated random numbers, test group and control group was selected

Inclusion criteria

- Age 18-65 yrs.
- Both sex
- ASA grade 1 and 2
- Elective surgery requiring overnight fasting of not less than 8 hours
- Written and informed consented patients

Exclusion criteria

- Reflux esophagitis
- BMI more than 30 kg/m²
- comorbidity linked to gastric motility like diabetes mellitus, Thyroid disease, GERD
- Patients who are taking gastric prokinetics
- Non fasting
- Undergoing gastrointestinal surgeries
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Equipments

1. Portable ultrasonography machine
2. Low frequency curvilinear probe (2-5 MHz)
3. Gauge pieces
4. Ultrasonography jelly

Pre anaesthesia evaluation was done for patients posted for elective surgeries and presenting complaints, comorbidities, gastrointestinal symptoms if any, personal and family history were noted along with height, weight, BMI, and all vital parameters. Study group were selected from those patients who satisfied the inclusion criteria. Patients who do not satisfy inclusion criteria were not accepted for study.

Informed consent was obtained after explaining the procedure and associated risk including risk of aspiration, intra operative hemodynamic changes and about possible delay in surgery. Epigastric region should be exposed while keeping chest and pelvic region covered.

Examiner should be standing on right side of patient with ultrasonography machine placed on left side of patient for easy probe manipulation and recording observations.

After confirming fasting status (minimum 8 hours), ultrasonography was done in the pre-operative room of operation theatre using a low frequency ultrasonography probe (2 –5 MHz) was used for ultrasonography examination. In supine position where transducer was held cephalad such that structures are displayed on left side of screen. After identifying liver, stomach and pancreas are identified and gastric antrum was identified just below left lobe of liver and pancreas. Patient was then repositioned in right lateral decubitus position for better visualization of gastric antrum caused by the gravitational descent of gastric content to antrum

An empty antrum appeared flat with juxtaposed anterior and posterior wall. Clear fluid in stomach appeared homogenous and hypoechoic, presence of hyperechoic air bubble corresponds to starry sky appearance.⁽⁷⁾

Antero-posterior (AP) and cranio-caudal (CC) diameter of antrum was noted after assessing content in gastric antrum. Cross section area (CSA) of antrum estimated from the above diameters using formula developed by Bolondi⁽⁸⁾

$$CSA = (AP \times CC \times 3.14) / 4$$

Gastric volumes was then estimated using the formula described by Perlas⁽⁹⁾

$$\text{Volumes (ml)} = 27.0 + 14.6 \times \text{right-lateral CSA} - 1.28 \times \text{age}$$

Above mentioned technique was used to obtain baseline gastric volumes i.e volumes before administration of oral fluids. The same technique was continued for ultrasonographic assessment of gastric antrum after giving 3ml/kg of 5% dextrose orally in group A patients and 4 ml/kg of 5% dextrose orally in group B patients at every 15 minutes until gastric volumes returned to baseline gastric volumes. Gastric volumes will be recorded in group C patients or control group at 0 minutes, 15 minutes and 30 minutes

after a minimum 8 hours of fasting to compare the test groups.

The data was coded and entered into Microsoft Excel spreadsheet. Analysis was done using IBM SPSS (SPSS Inc., IBM Corporation, NY, USA) Statistics Version 25 for Windows software program. Descriptive statistics included computation of percentages, means and standard deviations. The data were checked for normality before statistical analysis using Kolmogorov Simonov test. The ANOVA test (for quantitative data to compare two and more than two observations) was applied. The chi square test was used for qualitative data comparison of all clinical indicators. Level of significance was set at $P \leq 0.05$.

Sample size was estimated using method of two-way repeated measure of ANOVA by anticipating effect size of 0.10 between three groups across four time point and correlation among repeated measurements of 0.5, a minimum total sample size was estimated to be 60 in each at 5% level of significance and 90% power

Group A= 3 ml/kg

Group B= 4 ml/kg

Group C= no fluids

RESULTS

180 patients with 60 patients each in group A, B and C were examined using ultrasonography for measurement of gastric volumes after a minimum of 8 hour fasting. P value of gastric volumes between 3 groups at all intervals were more than 0.05, therefore gastric volume between all groups at all intervals were statistically insignificant. This implies that gastric volumes in all three groups were comparable at the start of study, at 15 minutes and at 30 minutes. In group B (4ml/kg), gastric volumes returned to baseline within 30 minutes in all except in 17 patients in whom baseline volumes was achieved within 45 minutes. So this observations were not comparable with group A and C where all patients achieved baseline gastric volume within 30 minutes. Mean gastric volumes of group B at 45 minutes was 76.29 ml.

Table 1. Demographic variables are represented in the tables below

	age (yr)	weight (Kg)	BMI	fasting (hr)	male	female
Group A	37.73	63.83	22.27	12.08	22	38
Group B	35.73	66.25	22.748	11.97	19	41
Group C	35.8	66.82	22.733	11.87	19	41

Table 2. Comparison of mean gastric antral diameters, antral area and gastric volumes taken prior to oral fluid administration (Baseline value)

		Mean	Std. Deviation	P value
AP (cm)	GROUP A	3.68	0.61	0.13
	GROUP B	3.67	0.57	
	GROUP C	3.58	0.62	
CC (cm)	GROUP A	2.33	0.56	0.16
	GROUP B	2.26	0.28	
	GROUP C	2.40	0.78	
CSA (mm ²)	GROUP A	6.67	1.56	0.47
	GROUP B	6.57	1.38	
	GROUP C	6.51	1.49	
GV (ml)	GROUP A	76.10	13.51	0.64
	GROUP B	76.35	12.28	
	GROUP C	76.31	13.75	

ANOVA test

Table 3. Comparison of mean gastric antral diameters, antral area and gastric volumes taken after oral fluid administration at 15th minute

		Mean	Std. Deviation	P value
AP (cm)	GROUP A	3.58	0.62	0.46
	GROUP B	3.701	0.51	
	GROUP C	3.65	0.48	
CC (cm)	GROUP A	2.43	0.63	0.14
	GROUP B	2.23	0.26	
	GROUP C	2.409	0.78	
CSA (cm ²)	GROUP A	6.74	1.57	0.73
	GROUP B	6.64	1.408	
	GROUP C	6.52	1.48	
GV (ml)	GROUP A	77.11	13.503	0.57
	GROUP B	78.91	12.45	
	GROUP C	76.46	13.703	

ANOVA test

Table 4. Comparison of mean gastric antral diameters, antral area and gastric volumes taken after oral fluid administration at 30th minute

Column1	Column2	Mean	Std. Deviation	P value
AP (cm)	GROUP A	3.83	0.59	0.49
	GROUP B	3.93	0.63	
	GROUP C	3.76	0.98	
CC (cm)	GROUP A	2.201	0.35	0.07
	GROUP B	2.11	0.253	
	GROUP C	2.23	0.26	
CSA (cm ²)	GROUP A	6.66	1.57	0.83
	GROUP B	6.55	1.36	

	GROUP C	6.507	1.49	
GV (ml)	GROUP A	76.01	13.52	0.98
	GROUP B	76.38	12.32	
	GROUP C	76.19	13.64	

ANOVA test

DISCUSSION

Preoperative fasting is a critical component of anaesthetic practice aimed at reducing the risk of pulmonary aspiration, particularly aspiration pneumonitis (Mendelson's syndrome)⁽¹⁰⁾, which can have significant morbidity. Traditional fasting guidelines recommend overnight fasting; however, recent research and updated guidelines emphasize individualized, evidence-based fasting protocols to avoid complications associated with both inadequate and prolonged fasting⁽⁶⁾.

Gastric emptying is a dynamic, multifactorial process influenced by neurohormonal regulation, the physical and chemical characteristics of ingested food or fluids, and patient-related factors such as age, gender, comorbidities, mood, and physical activity. Hormones like ghrelin promote gastric motility, whereas GLP-1 inhibits gastric emptying⁽¹¹⁾. An 'empty stomach' refers to a return of gastric contents to basal volume levels, generally considered safe for anaesthesia. Ultrasonography of the gastric antrum has emerged as a reliable, non-invasive tool to assess gastric contents and volume, replacing traditional, invasive methods.

In routine elective surgeries, patients often experience prolonged fasting due to scheduling delays. Prolonged fasting can cause discomfort, hypoglycaemia, dehydration, and anxiety. Enhanced Recovery After Surgery (ERAS) protocols recommend a more liberal approach to fasting, including clear fluids up to 2 hours before anaesthesia⁽⁵⁾. Studies, including the meta-analysis by Brady et al.⁽¹²⁾, have shown that shorter fasting durations for clear fluids are not associated with increased perioperative complications. This study was conducted to evaluate gastric volume and emptying time after administration of different volumes of clear fluids (5% dextrose) using ultrasonographic assessment in adult ASA I–II patients scheduled for elective surgery. Patients were randomized into three groups: Group A (3 ml/kg), Group B (4 ml/kg), and Group C

(fasting control). The gastric antrum was assessed in both supine and right lateral decubitus positions, with measurements taken at baseline, 15 and 30 minutes post-ingestion. Clear fluid appeared homogenous and hypoechoic on ultrasonography. An empty antrum appeared flat with juxtaposed anterior and posterior walls, and the presence of hyperechoic air bubbles gave a characteristic "starry sky" appearance. Right lateral positioning enhanced the detection of gastric contents due to gravitational pooling in the antrum⁽⁷⁾.

Our study found no statistically significant differences in antral cross-sectional area (CSA) or gastric volume between the three groups at any measured time point. At 15 minutes, gastric volumes were comparable between all groups, including the control group, suggesting that 3–4 ml/kg of 5% dextrose is effectively cleared within 15 minutes in most patients. By 30 minutes, gastric volumes had returned to baseline in all participants, with the exception of a small subset (28% in Group B) who reached baseline by 45 minutes. These findings support the use of 5% dextrose as a safe preoperative fluid when given in moderate quantities. Studies by Perlas et al.⁽⁹⁾ and Van de Putte et al.⁽¹³⁾ have established that gastric volume >1.5 ml/kg or CSA >7.5 cm² in the right lateral decubitus position is associated with increased aspiration risk. In our study, the mean CSA remained well below this threshold at all time points, and the calculated gastric volumes were consistent with baseline secretions rather than residual fluid load.

Patient characteristics such as age, BMI, and gender distribution were statistically comparable across the groups. Literature shows minimal influence of these variables on gastric emptying, which aligns with our results. For instance, Datz et al.⁽¹⁴⁾ reported slower gastric emptying in females, but the equal distribution across our study arms mitigated potential bias. Similarly, studies by Verdich et al.⁽¹⁵⁾ and Bonner et al.⁽¹⁶⁾ concluded that BMI and age, respectively, are not significant determinants of gastric emptying.

We excluded ASA III–IV patients to eliminate confounding due to comorbidities. Uncontrolled diabetes, for example, has been shown to alter gastric motility significantly. Our findings align with the guidelines of the Indian Society of Anaesthesiologists (ISA) ⁽⁶⁾, which recommend allowing clear liquids up to 2 hours before anaesthesia, limited to <450 ml. Our study used 5% dextrose at volumes of 3 ml/kg and 4 ml/kg, which were within this recommendation. Comparative studies by Sher-Lu Pai et al⁽¹⁷⁾, Liu et al.⁽¹⁸⁾ and Koppal et al. ⁽¹⁹⁾ also demonstrated that moderate preoperative fluid intake does not significantly alter gastric volumes or increase aspiration risk. Our study supports this and further narrows the timeframe by showing that even 4 ml/kg of clear fluids like 5% dextrose returns to baseline within 30–45 minutes.

The ultrasonographic assessment used formulas by Bolondi ⁽⁸⁾ for CSA and Perlas ⁽⁹⁾ for gastric volume estimation. These validated formulas are widely accepted and enhance the clinical applicability of our results. It can be concluded from the study that 5% dextrose at a moderate intake of 3ml/kg or 4ml/kg can maintain gastric volumes parameters comparable to that in fasting state. Therefore, these fluid regimens are comparable to fasting state in terms of gastric volumes parameter at given timeframe. The study also concluded that up to 4ml/kg can be given to patients up to 30 minutes prior to surgery in ASA 1 and 2 patients without significant risk of aspiration in absence of disease or co-morbidities that are known to reduce gastric emptying. Thus, fasting time for clear fluids can be reduced to 30 minutes for sedation and anaesthesia procedures without increasing the risk of aspiration. Further research is required to establish exact volumes of fluid which can be consumed prior to anaesthesia and sedation. Study also affirms that ultrasonographic measurement of gastric antrum can be a reliable technique to assess gastric volumes in day-to-day practice in patients who are at risk of aspiration .

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded from the study that 5% dextrose at a moderate intake of 3ml/kg or 4ml/kg can maintain gastric volume parameters comparable to that in fasting state. Therefore, these fluid regimens are

comparable to fasting state in terms of gastric volume parameter at given timeframe.

The study also concluded that up to 4ml/kg can be given to patients up to 30 minutes prior to surgery in ASA 1 and 2 patients without significant risk of aspiration in absence of disease or co-morbidities that are known to reduce gastric emptying. Thus, fasting time for clear fluids can be reduced to 30 minutes for sedation and anaesthesia procedures without increasing the risk of aspiration. Further research is required to establish exact volume of fluid which can be consumed prior to anaesthesia and sedation. Study also affirms that ultrasonographic measurement of gastric antrum can be a reliable technique to assess gastric volume in day-to-day practice in patients who are at risk of aspiration

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